

8T –Axions and the \mathcal{L} Theorem

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Abstract:

By analyzing the general idea behind the Axions, alongside the major features of the 8T, the author analyzes the problems with an idea. In addition, postulating the \mathcal{L} theorem which is related to expansion of the Lagrangian equation of motion, making it an innate feature of nature.

Introduction

Among the major features of the 8T, is the arbitrary variation term that vanish into matter, by mathematical proof. Such a feature can shed light on the subject of dark matter and, in particular, it can drastically reduce the number of options that can be considered a solution to that problem.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

The rule of dark matter was analyzed in the 8T, in two different ideas. The first idea was the Quark masses series, which dictate the direction of creation of matter particles. The original goal of the idea was to eliminate the question of the three families by searching for the series of families. Later in the thesis, the question of dark matter was analyzed via variational distributions, given by the packet. Let M_E denote the Einstein manifold, while the subscript is indexing the manifolds itself.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} \delta g_m - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} \delta g_n = 0$$

$$1 \leq m, n < k/2$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_n} \in [0,1]$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_m} \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{s_1} \neq \mathcal{R}^{s_2}$$

$$m = n$$

The variational distributions dictate the formation of matter cluster identical in size and different in configuration, while the mass series indicate the direction of families formation, indicating lower and lighter particle masses at each family below first generation, which is really third. The key point, which was not included in the thesis, is the following. The 8T indicating that nature is Lagrangian oriented, i.e. that it will generate only one class of matter, over infinite set of objects, i.e. manifolds. The main equation of the 8T, which allowed the constructing of the primordial, is clearly indicating that there is not another form of matter being created. That is in contrast to QFT and modern theories of physics that require:

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \cap \{\mathbb{W}\} \right); Z = 2$$

That is two sets, one for known matter, another one for weakly interacting massive particles, or Axions, denoted by \mathbb{W} . While the 8T has one infinity factor less than those theories as it requires only:

$$\left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \right) \forall s; \right) Z = 1$$

The problems with their theory are several. First, those theories are based upon observation, not on variational principle. In other words, the dark matter has to be **inserted** to the theory, and not derived from the innate axioms and equations, as the primordial third value was derived first and matched the observation later. Another way to state it, is that the theory should generate the major features of reality without observation or measurements but must match them perfectly afterwards. Both in particle scales and cosmological scales. The current theory of dark matter does not answer those qualifications criteria. Another major point is that the increase of one factor of infinity is a vital setback and a major theoretical fiasco. As the $Z = 2$ is synonymous with generating one infinity more of a new kind of Fermions, which is not the minimal class of particles needed for a Lagrangian oriented theory. Moreover, it does not provide **any reason** for the generation of the new kind of particles other than matching observational results. Why it has to be that way. Why two classes and not three and so on. Reasoning must be a fundamental value in a theory. If a theory cannot predict it first, it's innate nature is flawed and incomplete. In order to expend the idea of a Lagrangian oriented theory, one will postulate another theorem:

The (\mathcal{L}) Theorem – Nature would aspire to generate extremums on the classes of objects that it contains.

Using the following theorem, 8T is taking the Lagrangian equations to new horizons much beyond the spectra of physical nature, but make it an **innate feature** of nature. This feature is creating a demand on the object classes, principles and equations a theory must have. In particular, it demands nature to be described by extremums. With regards to the following features: minimal equations, minimal manifold classes, minimal kinds of matter, and on the contrary, maximal number of phenomena to be explained and predicted with those equations and classes. Using that feature of a Lagrangian orientation theory, the variational distributions combined with the masses series is seems simpler solution then to allocate another kind of particles, which breaks the Lagrangian demand on nature. It is the most Lagrangian oriented idea we have as $Z = 1$.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8T – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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